

ELEVATION PROFILE ESTIMATION FOR SINGLE PASS BI-STATIC SAR TOMOGRAPHY USING COMPRESSED SENSING

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ABSTRACT

Single-pass bistatic Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) Tomography (TomoSAR), in the case of a space-borne transmitter and a ground-based multi-channel receiver, can be used as an alternative to regular TomoSAR methods, which require multiple acquisitions (multi-pass) to derive elevation estimates from an observed scene. Generally, such systems utilize spectral-based reconstruction methods, which necessitate a large number of receiving elements or a limited number of elements arranged in a specific configuration to achieve the necessary resolution. In this study, we propose a novel approach for estimating the elevation profile using a reduced number of channels without a specific array configuration. We treat it as an underdetermined problem that can be solved using Compressed Sensing (CS) algorithms. The performance of the proposed approach is compared against the spectral-based approach using Monte Carlo simulations and demonstrated on real data measurements.

Index Terms— Sparse Reconstruction, OMP, Capon, DOA, SAR.

1. INTRODUCTION

SAR tomography is achieved by creating an additional synthetic aperture in the elevation direction by stacking multiple baseline observations (i.e., acquisitions from different elevation points) of a scene observed by a 2D SAR system. In general, to attain a very high resolution, several dozen acquisitions (multi-pass observations) are required. This track-to-track method, however, suffers from temporal decorrelation between the observed scenes, which can greatly affect the elevation estimate.

Single-track SAR tomography, can be considered an alternative to conventional TomoSAR. The concept with three antennas mounted across-track at an aeroplane and processing with a high-resolution method was first demonstrated in [1], followed by a series of publications in which high-resolution spectral estimation methods (MUSIC, CAPON,...) were investigated [2]. However, these methods generally suffer from high computation loads for large samples of data, required for

attaining sufficient resolution. A major step towards improving the resolution, with a limited number of samples, was the application of Compressive Sensing (CS) to several passages of a SAR satellite [3].

An effective way to deal with temporal decorrelations is by considering a Bistatic ground-based receiver configuration, where reception of the ground-reflected signal from a SAR satellite, is received by multiple ground-based receiving antennas. Each reception from the antenna is considered a baseline and since the receiving platform is stationary concerns related to co-registration between baselines are efficiently resolved. Ideally, the use of spectral-based approaches on ground-based systems requires a large number of uniformly spaced receivers or receivers in a specific arrangement, [4]. Sadly spectral-based estimators, methods with reduced channels suffer from sidelobes which may cause masking of closely spaced targets.

In this study, we propose a novel technique to estimate the elevation profile with a reduced number of channels (3 receivers), as an underdetermined problem via the use of CS algorithms. We circumvent the limitations on specific array geometries as required in [4], by choosing an array constellation of random/irregularly positioned placed elements. This in particular, is beneficial for CS-based methods as it allows the possibility for signals from different elevations to be distinguished relatively well - in contrast to a classical beamformer, where unacceptable side lobes would appear. We perform Monte Carlo simulations to present the probability of resolution which evaluates the likelihood of very closely spaced targets estimated accurately [5]. The robustness of the algorithm is evaluated using Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) for targets of different Signal-to-Noise-ratio (SNR) levels.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. In Section 2, the elevation estimation based on the DOA signal model and the two inversion methods applied to the bistatic case considered for the study has been discussed. Section 3 presents the simulation results obtained through Monte Carlo analysis, followed by the validation of the analysis using real data. Finally, the conclusions of the study are summarized in section 5.

2. THEORY

SAR tomography focuses on estimating the heights or elevations of scatterers and DOA estimation concentrates on estimating the angles or directions of the sources. Both problems rely on signal-processing techniques and often involve similar mathematical models and algorithms. For an array aperture composed of 'M' sensors, the signal recorded at different time instants can be formulated as

$$\mathbf{y}(t) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}(t) + \mathbf{n}(t) \quad (1)$$

where, matrix \mathbf{A} is a matrix of steering vectors corresponding to all receiving directions for each element of the array. $\mathbf{x}(t)$ represents a vector of source signals which have to be estimated and $\mathbf{n}(t)$ represents the complex additive white Gaussian noise.

When considering the DAO problem, every column of the \mathbf{A} , is a composition of steering vectors for a target present at an angle θ , which is given by

$$\mathbf{a}(\theta) = \exp(jk_0\mathbf{d}^T \sin(\theta)) \quad (2)$$

where, k_0 is a wavenumber corresponding to wavelength and \mathbf{d}^T is a vector inter-element spacing of size of $M \times 1$. Based on the choice of \mathbf{d}^T the receiver array can be configured. An extensive study on the types of array configurations can be found here [6].

When concerning tomographic processing techniques, the signal models of the steering vectors have to be modified to take into account the geometry of the measurement setup. In this study, we consider the Bi-static measurement setup of the COBIS architecture [7], an illustration of the same is provided in figure 1

Fig. 1: Bistatic tomographic geometry for single-pass tomography

With respect to geometry, a satellite is used as a transmitter of opportunity, M receiver elements arrangement in a vertical configuration with a total aperture of B_v , which allows forming a set of baselines separated with inter-element spacing \mathbf{d} . Each resolution cell can contain scattering sources located at different heights. R_1 and R_2 represent the slant

range and ground range. θ corresponds to the incidence angle for a specific resolution cell and B_N are the perpendicular baselines.

Hence the steering vector model from 2 can now be modified to take into account the geometry of the setup as

$$\mathbf{a}(\omega^i) = \exp(jk_0 \frac{\mathbf{B}_N}{R_2} h_i) \quad (3)$$

where h_i is the height to be estimated.

The elevation estimation problem can thus be formulated as

$$y = \sum_{i=1}^P \rho_i x_i \odot a(\omega^i) + n \quad (4)$$

where, P is the number of source, ρ_i is reflectivity of the i -th source, y the measurement acquired, x_i is the multiplicative noise, $a(\omega^i)$ the steering vector at the frequency ω^i associated with the height h_i and n the thermal noise.

When considering all measurements the model in equation (1), can be adapted for the elevation case by considering $\mathbf{A}(\omega)$, as a matrix of all possible steering vectors for all corresponding heights within the field of view.

2.1. Spectral Based Methods

Classically spectral-based estimators such as Capon employ the use of an estimated covariance matrix \mathbf{R} of the received signals. The covariance matrix captures the statistical relationships between the signals received at different array elements or sensors. The Capon filter is given by:

$$\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{Capon}(\omega) = \frac{\mathbf{a}^H(\omega)\hat{\mathbf{R}}^{-1}\mathbf{y}}{\mathbf{a}^H(\omega)\hat{\mathbf{R}}^{-1}\mathbf{a}(\omega)} \quad (5)$$

Though spectral-based estimation methods are effective in elevation profile estimation, they require a large number of receivers when resolving closely spaced targets, else suffer from sidelobes. In order to evaluate cases of resolving, close-spaced targets with a limited number of channels, we explore Sparse Reconstruction approaches by the use of CS algorithms.

2.2. Sparse Reconstruction Approach

Direction of Arrival (DOA) estimation, leverages the principles of CS to estimate the directions of signals in an array-based system using a reduced number of measurements. Provided the number of sources to be estimated in a scene is less than the number of measurements [5]. In the case of elevation estimation, not more than 2 high-rise buildings can be expected within a single range cell, satisfying the sparsity requirement of CS algorithms. Another requirement for the use of CS algorithms is related to the properties of the mapping matrix \mathbf{A} , also known as the "sensing matrix". The sensing

Fig. 2: The evolution of RMSE with increasing SNR for a scenario with two scatterers has been depicted in Figures 2a and 2c. It is evident from these figures that the CS approach effectively minimizes the estimation error, exhibiting superior performance for both lower SNR values and scenarios with closely spaced targets ($\delta h \leq 0.2m$). On the other hand, as anticipated, spectral-based approaches necessitate a greater number of receivers to achieve comparable results. Furthermore, these methods require higher SNR values. Figure 2b demonstrates that spectral-based methods and CS-based methods yield equivalent results when the targets are separated by $\delta h = 0.8m$. However, in Figure 2d, spectral methods fail to resolve or accurately detect the targets, while CS-based methods exhibit greater resilience in such cases

matrix has to satisfy the Restricted Isometry property (RIP) or should be designed to have low mutual coherence, detailed information on this topic can be found in [6]. In the context of this study, we chose an arbitrary array constellation, which results in a lower mutual coherence than a regular ULA configuration. This circumvents the requirement for any specific array geometry, as required in the case of spectral-based methods. We considered the CS algorithm Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (OMP) adapted for the elevation estimation case, considered as in **Algorithm 1**, to exploit the sparsity of the spectrum to recover the underlying coefficients corresponding to the elevation profile.

Algorithm 1 Orthogonal Matching Pursuit (OMP) for Elevation Estimation

- Require:** \mathbf{y} , $\mathbf{A}(\omega)$, Number of desired estimates, K
- 1: Initialize estimated vector $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$, as an empty set
 - 2: Set the residual vector, \mathbf{r} , to the received signal vector
 - 3: **for** $i = 1$ **to** K **do**
 - 4: Find the index j that maximizes $|\langle \mathbf{r}^{(i-1)}, \mathbf{A}(\omega)_{\cdot j} \rangle|$
 - 5: Update the support set: $\mathcal{S} = \mathcal{S} \cup \{j\}$
 - 6: Solve the least squares problem: $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{\mathcal{S}} = \arg \min_{\mathbf{z}} \|\mathbf{y} - \mathbf{A}(\omega)_{\mathcal{S}} \mathbf{z}\|_2$
 - 7: Update the estimate: $\hat{\mathbf{x}} = \mathbf{0}$, $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_{\mathcal{S}} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_{\mathcal{S}}$
 - 8: Update the residual: $\mathbf{r}^{(i)} = \mathbf{y} - \mathbf{A}(\omega) \hat{\mathbf{x}}$
 - 9: **end for**
 - 10: **Return** estimated sparse coefficients: $\hat{\mathbf{x}}$
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3. RESULTS

3.1. Simulations

For a synthetic case of estimating the elevation profile of two targets for the considered single-pass bistatic ground-based

receiver configuration. We consider the receiver array to consist of 3 omnidirectional antennas operating under ideal conditions. The resolution cell under test is considered at a ground range of 60m from the measurement setup. The maximum number of scatters inside a single-resolution cell is limited to 2. The results are evaluated for a fixed aperture of $3d$, with $d = 0.867m$, where 3 configurations of receivers discretise the aperture. The first has 4 receivers with uniform spacing $[0,1d,2d,3d]$, the second has 3 receivers with uniform spacing $[0,1.5d,3d]$ and the final configuration with 3 receivers, where the central element occupies an arbitrary position between $[0,3d]$. Every element has a minimum of $\lambda/4$ spacing. The metrics; Probability of resolution, which quantifies the likelihood that an algorithm can successfully resolve or differentiate between distinct components within a measurement [5] and Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), which provides a measure of how closely the predicted or estimated values align with the true values, are used to evaluate the proposed methods. The results of the analysis can be seen in figures 3 and 2 respectively.

3.2. Experimental results

The CS methods were applied to the datasets obtained from bistatic single-pass experiments conducted with the ground receiver, as described in [7]. In these experiments, the satellite Sentinel-1A/B was used as a transmitter of opportunity, and the bistatic receiver, COBIS, was deployed. The antennas corresponding to each available channel were vertically distributed with a separation of $[0, d, 3d]$, where $d = 0.867m$ represented the longest baseline of 2.601m.

The measurements were acquired on 2021.06.25 within the time interval of 04:29:30-04:30:03. The ground truth associated with the two scatters in the measurement dataset indicated a differential height of 1.43m. The results are presented in figure 4.

Fig. 3: The minimum separation required to resolve two scatterers, considering a fixed SNR, has been analyzed. Our findings reveal that the CS approach is capable of resolving two targets with a minimum separation of 0.18m, utilizing only 3 receivers. In contrast, Spectral-based approaches necessitate an additional receiver to achieve an equivalent result.

Fig. 4: We observe that Spectral estimator exhibited side lobes, which caused false detections. The estimated differential height is 1.2 meters. In contrast, the CS approach provided a more precise estimate of the scatterers with a differential height of 1.39 meters.

4. CONCLUSION

This study presents the application of CS-based algorithms as an effective alternative to spectral-based methods in the context of single-pass bistatic TomoSAR. Monte Carlo simulations were employed to evaluate the algorithms. The results reveal that the CS-based method, specifically OMP, outperforms the spectral-based Capon method, even when both methods utilize arrays with the same number of elements. To assess the ability of the algorithms in resolving closely spaced

targets, the metric Probability of Resolution was employed. The results demonstrate that OMP exhibits superior performance compared to Capon in resolving close-spaced targets. The concept was tested on the Sentinel-1A/B dataset, which validates the findings of the study.

5. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No.860370.

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